

Enhancing Fraud Detection: A Comprehensive Analysis of Financial Transactions

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Abstract

This project focused on the analysis and interpretation of a large financial transactions dataset created by Caixabank Tech for the 2024 AI Hackathon, available on the website Kaggle. The research involved developing an interactive Tableau dashboard, which included maps of financial transactions across the United States and the world. In addition to data visualization, I identified suitable statistical techniques for analysis and applied statistical models and machine learning methods to predict fraudulent transactions within the dataset. Those statistical models and machine learning techniques were logistic regression, decision tree, random forest, and neural network. The goal of this research was to evaluate the performance of these four methods in predicting fraudulent transactions.

Key Words: Fraud Detection, Data Visualization, Financial Transactions, Statistical Models, Machine Learning Techniques

1. Introduction

Every person is susceptible to fraud. With the increase in online presence, there has been a lot of fraud occurring with online information including medical records, transportation, and financial transactions. To solve these problems, there has been a need for people who are knowledgeable in cybersecurity. Cybersecurity is the practice of protecting computer systems, networks, and data from any digital damage, attacks, or unauthorized access. Cybersecurity protects the user's personal information. One type of fraud that is prevalent is financial fraud. Without proper cybersecurity, a hacker can get a person's banking information and make unauthorized purchases under their name. This can lead to that person potentially losing thousands of dollars. It is important to know as soon as possible if a fraudulent transaction occurs. Using datasets of transactions that are known to be fraudulent, a data analyst can create a model to predict if future transactions are fraudulent or not. That data analyst must choose which model will be the best at accurately predicting fraudulent transactions. This master's thesis was an exploration through the field of data analytics, which is a process that involves using various software and techniques to identify trends and patterns within datasets. This research incorporated industry-standard software, such as Tableau, Anaconda, Python, and R. The goal of this research was to evaluate the performance of four statistical models and machine learning techniques in predicting fraudulent transactions.

To start this research, I selected a banking transactions dataset available on Kaggle, a platform that provides resources and tools for machine learning and data science. The banking transactions dataset was created by Caixabank Tech for the 2024 AI Hackathon, an event where participants address real-world problems using machine learning and artificial intelligence. The dataset "combines transaction records, customer information, and card data from a banking institution, spanning across the 2010s decade." This dataset is exceptionally large. It includes twelve columns: ID, date, client ID, card ID, amount, use chip, merchant ID, merchant city, merchant state, zip, mcc (merchant category code), errors. The dataset has 13,305,915 observations. Figure 1 shows the beginning rows of this dataset.

id	date	client_id	card_id	amount	use_chip	merchant_id	merchant_city	merchant_state	zip	mcc	errors	target	Location	Response
7475327	2010-01-01 00:01:00	1556	2972	-77.00	Swipe Transaction	59935	Beulah	ND	58523	5499	NA	No	inperson	0
7475328	2010-01-01 00:02:00	561	4575	14.57	Swipe Transaction	67570	Bettendorf	IA	52722	5311	NA	No	inperson	0
7475329	2010-01-01 00:02:00	1129	102	80.00	Swipe Transaction	27092	Vista	CA	92084	4829	NA	No	inperson	0
7475332	2010-01-01 00:06:00	848	3915	46.41	Swipe Transaction	13051	Hanwood	MD	20776	5813	NA	No	inperson	0
7475333	2010-01-01 00:07:00	1807	165	4.81	Swipe Transaction	20519	Bronx	NY	10464	5942	NA	No	inperson	0
7475335	2010-01-01 00:14:00	1684	2140	26.46	Online Transaction	39021	ONLINE	NA	NA	4784	NA	No	online	0
7475338	2010-01-01 00:23:00	554	3912	3.51	Swipe Transaction	67570	Pearland	TX	77581	5311	NA	No	inperson	0
7475339	2010-01-01 00:23:00	605	5061	2.58	Swipe Transaction	75781	Brooklyn	NY	11210	5411	NA	No	inperson	0
7475340	2010-01-01 00:26:00	1556	2972	39.63	Swipe Transaction	59935	Beulah	ND	58523	5499	NA	No	inperson	0
7475341	2010-01-01 00:27:00	1797	1127	43.33	Swipe Transaction	33326	Kahului	HI	96732	4121	NA	No	inperson	0
7475342	2010-01-01 00:30:00	114	3398	49.42	Swipe Transaction	61195	North Hollywood	CA	91606	5541	NA	No	inperson	0
7475344	2010-01-01 00:32:00	646	2093	73.79	Swipe Transaction	1636	Erie	PA	16511	7538	NA	No	inperson	0
7475345	2010-01-01 00:32:00	1129	5492	100.00	Swipe Transaction	27092	Vista	CA	92084	4829	NA	No	inperson	0
7475346	2010-01-01 00:34:00	394	4717	26.04	Online Transaction	39021	ONLINE	NA	NA	4784	NA	No	online	0
7475347	2010-01-01 00:36:00	114	3398	-64.00	Swipe Transaction	61195	North Hollywood	CA	91606	5541	NA	No	inperson	0
7475348	2010-01-01 00:36:00	1376	2182	54.27	Swipe Transaction	88945	Cedar Park	TX	78613	5813	NA	No	inperson	0
7475349	2010-01-01 00:37:00	1682	238	20.74	Swipe Transaction	21586	Grand Forks	ND	58201	5411	NA	No	inperson	0
7475350	2010-01-01 00:38:00	114	3398	64.00	Swipe Transaction	61195	North Hollywood	CA	91606	5541	NA	No	inperson	0

Figure 1: First Several Rows of Dataset

Since the dataset was so big with 13,305,915 observations, I first created samples that would be easier and quicker to run tests on. I created two samples of this dataset titled Hunsamp and Tensamp. The Hunsamp dataset was a sample of the whole dataset in which every hundredth observation was chosen. The Tensamp dataset was a sample of the whole dataset in which every tenth observation was chosen. The Hunsamp dataset contained 133,060 observations, and the Tensamp dataset contained 1,330,592 observations. To prepare all three datasets, there was a small amount of data cleaning. The amount column was initially classified as character, so the dollar signs were removed, and its class was changed to numeric. A “Response” column was added in which errors were turned into one and non-errors were turned into zero. A “Transaction Type” column was created to categorize if a transaction was in-person or online. A “Location” column was created to categorize if a transaction was inside the United States or outside the United States. Lastly, when predicting fraudulent transactions, the entire transactions dataset was merged with a JSON file that labeled which transactions were fraudulent or not. However, the JSON file did not contain fraud labels for all 13,305,915 observations. It only labeled 8,914,963 observations as fraudulent or not. Thus, in the final analysis the labeled 8,914,963 observations were used as a training dataset for the model. The model was then applied to the remaining 4,390,952 observations to predict which ones were fraudulent or not.

2. Literature Review

The world is constantly evolving and with that new problems arise. According to Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman (2017), the advent of computers has caused statistical problems to explode with size and complexity. Statisticians have been creating different statistical methods to evaluate trends in data to better understand and solve problems. With the introduction of artificial intelligence, there have also been creations of machine learning methods to understand these problems and solve them in a faster, more efficient way. Hastie, Tibshirani, and Friedman (2017) took these new ideas and explained them in a statistical framework for their book *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. Peter Bruce and Andrew Bruce (2017) also wrote about the importance of these statistical methods in their book but incorporated how software can aid in the analysis. They specifically used the software R to run the statistical methods on their data. In addition to R, there is also other software that can perform these same statistical methods and machine learning. In this research, both RStudio and Python Spyder were used.

With the creation of so many new methods of analyzing data, there is the question of how we can apply these methods, and which one works best. In 2010, Goldbloom and Hammer created the website Kaggle. On Kaggle, there are various machine learning competitions in which people, either individually or part of a team, build and train models to make predictions. The model will be tested on its accuracy and the model with the highest accuracy will be the winner. These competitions allow people to collaborate with each other and test which models are more useful in certain situations. For example, Peter Bruce and Andrew Bruce (2017) explained how some situations are

considered rare class problems. Rare class problems are when there is an imbalance in the dataset, meaning there are many more cases in one class versus another. The detection of fraudulent transactions is an example of a rare class problem because there are usually significantly more non-fraudulent transactions as opposed to fraudulent transactions. Accuracy is the percentage of correctly predicted fraud and non-fraud transactions by the model. Thus, a model with high accuracy may not be the best fit for this situation since it may only have high accuracy in correctly predicting non-fraudulent transactions. The ratio of accurately predicted non-fraudulent transactions is the sensitivity. A model may not predict the number of fraudulent transactions very well. One may be happy with a model that is less accurate overall, but more accurate in predicting fraudulent transactions. The specificity of a model is the ratio of accurately predicted fraudulent transactions. Thus, a person may desire a model with a higher specificity.

Afriyie, et al. (2023) conducted a study in which they evaluated the performance of logistic regression, decision trees, and random forests in predicting fraudulent transactions in a banking transactions dataset. To solve the problem of class imbalance, they decided to under-sample the non-fraudulent transactions. Their goal was to see which method worked best in predicting fraudulent transactions and find ways to prevent fraudulent transactions from occurring. To evaluate each method, they observed the accuracy, precision, recall/sensitivity, specificity, and F1 score. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall of the model. Their conclusion was that the random forest model performed better than the logistic regression and decision tree models.

Salunke, et al. (2025) conducted a more recent study also comparing the performances of logistic regression, decision tree, and random forest models in predicting fraudulent financial transactions. To evaluate each method, they observed the accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC-ROC). They determined that the logistic regression model struggled to capture the complex patterns in the dataset, which made it weak in determining the fraudulent transactions. The decision tree model was good at capturing the relationship between the variables that contributed to a fraudulent transaction but were prone to overfitting. The random forest model utilized multiple decision trees, which fixed the overfitting problem. The random forest model performed the best out of the three. After testing each method, they used the stacking method to combine the three models into one meta model. The meta model input data through all three models simultaneously. Each model made its own prediction, and the meta-model generated a final prediction based on those results. The meta model had the best results out of all the models.

Randhawa, et al. (2018) evaluated the performances of various models in credit card fraud detection. They used the Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), which is a metric that considers the true and false positives and negatives, to evaluate each model. Based on the results of their experiment, the random forest model performed better than the logistic regression model. Prajwala T R (2015) also conducted a study in which she evaluated the performance of decision trees and random forests created in R. She used a weather dataset along with the models to predict rainfall. She concluded that the random forest method worked better at predicting rainfall, but took a much longer time to run the code in R. This fact makes sense because the random forests are created using multiple decision trees.

In addition to logistic regression, decision trees and random forests, neural networks are another method for fraud detection. Neural networks are a machine learning technique in which the machine will learn patterns from a training dataset and use that knowledge to predict fraudulent transactions in a new dataset. Malik, et al. (2024) published a paper whose aim was to explore the application of machine learning in credit risk assessment and fraud detection. Through examining existing methodologies, analyzing experimental results, and discussing potential implications, they established that machine learning has much potential. It will improve efficiency and enable more informed decision making for detecting fraud.

Randhawa, et al. (2018) used the models of support vector machine, logistic regression, genetic programming and probabilistic neural network to identify financial statement fraud. Based on their results, they were able to conclude that the probabilistic neural network model performed the best.

Mienye and Jere (2024) also conducted a study of the various types of machine learning techniques. They evaluated the performances of deep learning neural networks, which are neural networks that consist of multiple hidden layers. Each type of neural network was compared based on its accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, and F1 score. Their results showed high performance in predicting non-fraudulent transactions, but poor performance in predicting fraudulent transactions. This was attributed to the imbalance in the dataset. For my research, I compared how logistic regression, decision trees, random forests, and neural networks perform fraud detection.

3. Methodology

3.1 Data Visualization

This research started with a data visualization of the banking transactions dataset. This data visualization was a representation of the descriptive statistics. It was created in Tableau in the form of an interactive dashboard. Tableau is a visual analytics platform in which users can create an interactive visual of a dataset. Tableau Public allows users to share their own interactive dashboards and look at what other people have created. The interactive dashboard for this thesis uses bar plots to compare transactions of four different card brands and three different card types. Bar plots are also used to compare the several types of errors that occur during a transaction. The interactive dashboard also contains a map of the location of each transaction. For the map, there are two different sections: United States Map and World Map. For the map, you can hover or click on each state or country to get information about what transactions occurred there. The interactive dashboard compares the sum, average, and count of transactions for both inside the United States and outside the United States.

3.2 Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a statistical model used to predict a binary outcome. The model works by creating an equation that predicts the probability of a target variable belonging to a certain class using one or more predictor variables. The logistic regression model is

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \beta_3x_3 + \dots + \beta_nx_n,$$

where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ are the model coefficients and x_1, \dots, x_n are the predictor variables. The log-odds function, also known as the logit function $\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right)$, maps the probability p from $(0, 1)$ to any value $(-\infty, +\infty)$, where p is the probability of fraud transaction. The number of predictor variables, n , can vary depending on the model. For this thesis, logistic regression was used to predict whether a transaction is fraudulent or not. If the predicted probability p from the equation is above a certain threshold, then that transaction is classified as fraudulent. Otherwise, the transaction is classified as non-fraudulent. I chose the threshold to be 0.8 for logistic regression and all future methods.

3.3 Decision Tree and Random Forest

A decision tree is a machine learning algorithm that asks a series of yes or no questions and eventually determines a binary outcome depending on the answers to those questions. A decision tree starts with a root node which splits into two internal nodes called decision nodes. Each decision node splits into two more decision nodes. This process continues until the tree reaches a leaf node. A leaf node represents an outcome in the dataset. For example, a decision tree may be created to determine if an email is spam or not depending on whether the email has specific phrases and words. In that case, the leaf nodes represent whether the email is spam or not. Figure 2 shows the structure of a decision tree. Decision trees can be prone to overfitting. Overfitting means that the model knows the training dataset too well, rather than just the underlying patterns. As a result, when the model is used on a new dataset, it will not perform well. The decision trees can also continue to grow and become more complex if not limited. This can result in longer computation times.

Figure 2: Decision Tree

For this thesis, each of the decision nodes was related to the variables in the dataset. I specifically chose five variables to determine whether the transaction was fraudulent or not. Those variables were amount, use of chip (swipe transaction or online transaction), zip code, merchant category code (mcc), and location (online or in-person). The leaf nodes were either a fraudulent transaction or a non-fraudulent transaction.

Random forests are a machine learning technique that uses multiple decision trees to determine a binary outcome. Each decision tree makes a prediction. Then the random forest will predict the outcome by averaging the results from all the decision trees. The number of decision trees can vary depending on the model. For this thesis, I used random forests with either 10, 50, or 100 decision trees. Figure 3 depicts the structure of a random forest.

Figure 3: Random Forest

3.4 Neural Network

A neural network is a machine learning program that mimics how our brain works. Neural networks make predictions by analyzing training samples, similar to how we make decisions based on our past experiences. One of the best-known neural networks is Google’s search engine. Neural networks are also used to create artificial intelligence. Neural networks consist of layers of nodes, or neurons, that will process the training dataset and learn any patterns. The number of layers can vary depending on the model. For this research, I used neural networks with either 50 or 100 layers. Each node can be connected to one or several other nodes in the layers above and below it. Most of today’s neural networks are “feed forward” in which they will feed data forward through the nodes.

Figure 4 shows the structure of a neural network with two hidden layers. The nodes are connected to each other through parameter values that are initially chosen randomly. Once the training data is input into the neural network, a method called backpropagation is used to estimate these unknown parameters. Within each node there is an activation function. Some examples of activation functions are the soft plus, rectified linear unit (ReLU), and sigmoid shape. In practice, it is common to use the ReLU or soft plus activation functions. The ReLU function is defined as $f(x) = \max(0, x)$. It turns all negative numbers into 0. The soft plus function is defined as $f(x) = \ln(1 + e^x)$. The output of the soft plus function is also always positive. The sigmoid shape activation function is defined as $\sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}}$. This function is S shaped and maps any real number to a number between 0 and 1. For this research, I utilized the ReLU function. The activation function creates a boundary between the different cases. In this research, the neural network was used to predict fraudulent transactions in the banking transactions dataset.

Figure 4: Neural Network

3.5 Software

These four statistical models and machine learning techniques were performed using both RStudio and Python Spyder. RStudio is a multifunctional open-source IDE (integrated developmental environment) that is used for working with the programming language R. Users must download both R and RStudio to utilize RStudio. R is an open-source statistical software and programming language used for statistics and data analysis. Both programs are free to download. The RStudio version that I used in this research was 2024.12.1+563. Python Spyder is an open-source cross platform IDE. It is designed for scientists, data analysts, and engineers. Python Spyder is also completely free to download. One of the easier ways to download Python Spyder is by downloading Anaconda Navigator, which is a desktop graphical user interface (GUI) that allows users to launch various applications including Python Spyder, PyCharm, and Jupyter. The Python Spyder version I used in this research was 6.0.7.

This research was done on an Acer Nitro 5 laptop. The laptop's processor is an AMD Ryzen 5 4600H with Radeon Graphics. The installed RAM is 8.00 GB. The graphics card is NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1650, AMD Radeon™ Graphics. There is 238 GB of storage on the laptop.

4. Results of Data Visualization and Data Analysis

4.1 Dashboard of Data Visualization

The data visualization dashboard was posted to Tableau Public for anyone to view. The link is https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/juliana.patrone/viz/Thesis_17405173183860/UnitedStatesSum. The data visualization contains tabs with a United States map and a world map. Within each map, there is an option to see the sum of transactions, the average amount in each transaction, and the number of transactions that occurred. There is a bar graph in the bottom left corner that

compares four different card brands: Amex, Discover, MasterCard, and Visa. Below that chart is another bar graph that compares the three different card types: Debit, Credit, and Debit (Prepaid). The bottom right corner has a bar graph comparing the several types of errors that occurred. Below are some screenshots of the data visualization made in Tableau. (Figure 5)

Figure 5.a: United States Sum of Transactions

Figure 5.b: World Map Sum of Transactions

Figure 5.c: United States Sum of Transactions for Texas

Figure 5.d: World Map Number of Transactions

Figure 5: Data Visualization

4.2 Results of Logistic Regression

I started logistic regression models to evaluate how significant single variables were to predict transactions with errors. Through testing the different variables that could contribute to a transaction with an error, I decided to create a logistic regression equation using amount, type of transaction, and location as the predictor variables. The target variable was errors. The logistic regression model for the Hunsamp dataset is

$$\log\left(\frac{\hat{p}}{1-\hat{p}}\right) = -4.3771 + 0.0015x_1 + 0.5752x_2 + 0.0882x_3,$$

where x_1 is amount, x_2 is type of transaction, and x_3 is location. The p-values for amount, type of transaction, and location are displayed in Table 1 below.

Table 1: P-Values for Hunsamp Logistic Regression Model

Variable Name	Estimate	P-Value
Amount	0.0015	< 0.0001
Type of Transaction	0.5752	0.00262
Location	0.0882	0.63425

The p-values for amount, type of transaction, and location were <0.0001, 0.00262, and 0.63425 respectively. These analysis results show that the amount and type of transaction were significant, but location was not.

The logistic regression equation for the Tensamp dataset was

$$\log\left(\frac{\hat{p}}{1-\hat{p}}\right) = -4.367 + 0.001459x_1 + 0.5302x_2 + 0.01029x_3,$$

where x_1 is amount, x_2 is type of transaction, and x_3 is location. The p-values for amount, type of transaction, and location are displayed in Table 2.

Table 2: P-Values for Tensamp Logistic Regression Model

Variable Name	Estimate	P-Value
Amount	0.001459	< 0.0001
Type of Transaction	0.5302	< 0.0001
Location	0.01029	0.081

The p-values for amount, type of transaction, and location were <0.0001, <0.0001, and 0.081 respectively. Based on the analysis result, we conclude that the amount and type of transaction were significant, but location was not.

The logistic regression equation for the whole dataset was

$$\log\left(\frac{\hat{p}}{1-\hat{p}}\right) = -4.319 + 0.001515x_1 + 0.4591x_2 + 0.06252x_3,$$

where x_1 is amount, x_2 is type of transaction, and x_3 is location. The p-values for amount, type of transaction, and location are displayed in Table 3.

Table 3: P-Values for Whole Dataset Logistic Regression Model

Variable Name	Estimate	P-Value
Amount	0.001515	< 0.0001
Type of Transaction	0.4591	< 0.0001
Location	0.06252	0.000622

The p-values for amount, type of transaction, and location were <0.0001, <0.0001, and 0.000622 respectively. The analysis results show that the amount, type of transaction, and location were significant.

When the first logistic regression model was used to predict the transactions with errors in the Hunsamp dataset, it only predicted one transaction with an error, while there were 2,079 transactions with errors. The specificity of this model was close to 0%, therefore, it fails to predict the fraud transactions.

Python Spyder was able to give the same logistic regression equations as RStudio, but in a different amount of time. The time to create the logistic regression equation for the Hunsamp and Tensamp datasets was slightly faster in RStudio. However, the time to create the logistic regression equation for the whole dataset was significantly faster in Python Spyder. RStudio took a little under five minutes to run this code compared to only one minute in Python Spyder. Table 4 compares the running times to create the logistic regression equations for each dataset in the two software.

Table 4: Running Time for Logistic Regressions

Data	RStudio	Python Spyder
Hunsamp	0.46 sec	0.56 sec
Tensamp	5.27 sec	6.30 sec
Whole Dataset	288.45 sec (4.81 min)	60.08 sec

The logistic regression code was redone in Python Spyder with the entire banking transactions dataset combined with the JSON file that was also downloaded off Kaggle titled train fraud labels. This file labeled which transactions were fraud or not. Rather than predicting which transactions had an error, logistic regression was now used to predict if the entire transaction was fraudulent or not. The second time running this code, I used five variables from the dataset: amount, use of chip, zip code, mcc, and location. These same five variables are used in the rest of the methods for analysis. The new logistic regression equation was

$$\log\left(\frac{\hat{p}}{1-\hat{p}}\right) = -5.1578 + 0.0023x_1 - 0.5757x_2 - (8.019e^{-5})x_3 + (4.143e^{-5})x_4 +$$

$0.5814x_5,$

where x_1 is amount, x_2 is use of chip, x_3 is zip code, x_4 is mcc, and x_5 is location. The p-values for these variables are displayed in the table below (Table 5).

Table 5: P-Values for Logistic Regression Model Redone

Variable Name	Estimates	P-Value
Amount	0.0023	< 0.0001
Use of Chip	-0.5757	< 0.0001
Zip Code	$8.019e^{-5}$	< 0.0001
MCC	$4.143e^{-5}$	< 0.0001
Location	0.5814	< 0.0001

All the p-values were extremely close to zero, which indicates that all these predictor variables are significant for predicting the probability of fraud transactions. When this logistic regression model was used to predict which transactions were fraudulent or not, it performed better than the first logistic regression model. This model predicted 20 fraudulent transactions out of 13,332 total fraudulent transactions. However, this was still not a particularly effective way of predicting fraudulent transactions. The overall accuracy of this model was 0.9985 since the model accurately predicted 8,901,560 non-fraudulent transactions out of 8,901,631 total non-fraudulent transactions. However, the specificity, which is the accuracy of predicted fraud transactions, was 0.0015. This indicates that this method needs to be improved upon or not used to predict fraudulent transactions. When the code was run in RStudio, the logistic regression model performed about the same as in Python. However, in Python, the code took about 53.09 seconds to run, while in RStudio, it took about 11 minutes to run. Table 6 compares the accuracies, specificities, and sensitivities of this logistic regression model.

Table 6: Logistic Regression Results for Combined Dataset

Data	Combined Dataset		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Python	0.9985	0.0015	0.999992
RStudio	0.9985	0.0027	1

4.3 Results of Decision Tree and Random Forest

The decision tree was first created after the logistic regression model. The datasets were split into a training dataset and a testing dataset. The decision tree was then built using five predictor variables: amount, use of chip, zip code, mcc, and location, and applied to the testing dataset to test the number of transactions that had an error. For the Hunsamp dataset, the decision tree predicted 29 transactions with errors out of 506 total transactions with errors. It had an overall accuracy of 0.9706. Its specificity was 0.0573 and sensitivity was 0.9847. Notice how the overall accuracy of this model is very close to 100%, but the specificity is very close to 0%. This indicates that the model did not

perform well in predicting errors. This model may not have performed well because the decision tree was not limited. It grew big and complicated as can be seen in Figure 6. This can be a sign of overfitting.

Figure 6: Decision Tree for Hundred Sample

There were similar results when creating decision trees for the Tensamp and whole datasets. For the Tensamp dataset, the decision tree accurately predicted 308 transactions with errors out of 5,193 total transactions with errors. It had an overall accuracy of 0.9719, specificity of 0.0593, and sensitivity of 0.9864. For the whole dataset, the decision tree accurately predicted 6,391 transactions with errors out of 52,821 total transactions with errors. It had an overall accuracy of 0.9756, specificity of 0.12099, and sensitivity of 0.9895.

I had to slightly change the code when converting it to RStudio from Python. I had to add a maximum depth of 30 for the decision tree so the code would run properly. RStudio performed about the same as Python Spyder in creating the decision trees and predicting the transactions with errors. For the Hunsamp dataset, RStudio's decision tree accurately predicted 21 transactions with errors out of 549 total transactions with errors. The decision tree had an overall accuracy of 0.9711, specificity of 0.0383, and sensitivity of 0.9867. For the Tensamp dataset, RStudio's decision tree accurately predicted 95 transactions with errors out of 5,372 total transactions with errors. The decision tree had an overall accuracy of 0.9836, specificity of 0.0177, and sensitivity of 0.9994. For the entire dataset, RStudio's decision tree accurately predicted 918 transactions with errors out of 52,798 total transactions with errors. The decision tree had an overall accuracy of 0.9844, specificity of 0.0174, and sensitivity of 0.9999. Table 7 lists the accuracies, specificities, and sensitivities of the decision trees for each dataset in each software.

Table 7: Results for Decision Trees

Data	Python			RStudio		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Hunsamp	0.9706	0.0573	0.9847	0.9711	0.0383	0.9867
Tensamp	0.9719	0.0593	0.9864	0.9836	0.0177	0.9994
Whole Datasets	0.9756	0.12099	0.9895	0.9844	0.0174	0.9999

The running times for the code in each software were significantly different. Python Spyder created the decision trees much faster than RStudio. The code averaged 17.5 minutes to create the decision tree for the whole dataset in RStudio. Python Spyder only averaged 1.48 minutes to create a decision tree. Table 8 compares the running times to create the decision tree for each dataset in the two software.

Table 8: Running Time for Decision Trees

Data	RStudio	Python Spyder
Hunsamp	5.36 sec	0.3724 sec
Tensamp	79.99 sec	6.6277 sec
Whole Dataset	1052.92 sec (17.55 min)	88.87 sec (1.48 min)

The decision tree was redone with the entire banking transactions dataset combined with the JSON file that was also downloaded off Kaggle titled train fraud labels. The decision tree model now predicts whether a transaction is fraudulent or non-fraudulent. The decision tree accurately predicted 1,798 fraudulent transactions out of 3,294 total fraudulent transactions. The decision tree had an overall accuracy of 0.9989, specificity of 0.5458, and sensitivity of 0.9995. This decision tree had a much higher specificity than logistic regression. The average time to run this code was 48 seconds. When running in RStudio, the decision tree accurately predicted 1,132 fraudulent transactions out of 3,311 total fraudulent transactions. This model had an overall accuracy of 0.9989, specificity of 0.3419, and sensitivity of 1. RStudio averaged 4.6 minutes to run this code. The accuracies, specificities, and sensitivities of these two models are compared in Table 9. Python Spyder was more accurate in predicting fraudulent transactions and had a faster running time than RStudio. The decision tree model was better at predicting fraudulent transactions than the logistic regression model.

Table 9: Decision Tree Results for Combined Dataset

Data	Combined Dataset		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Python	0.9989	0.5458	0.9995
RStudio	0.9989	0.3419	1

The next method I used was the random forest machine learning technique. I created random forests for all three datasets using 10, 50, and 100 decision trees. The code for random forests was first done in Python Spyder. Table 10 below summarizes the results for the random forests with 10 and 50 trees. For the Hunsamp dataset, the random forest with 10 decision trees accurately predicted 11 transactions with an error out of 506 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.9821 with a specificity of 0.0217 and sensitivity of 0.9969. With 50 decision trees, the random forest accurately predicted 8 transactions with an error out of 506 total transactions with an error. This random forest model had an accuracy of 0.9819 with a specificity of 0.0158 and sensitivity of 0.9968. With 100 decision trees, the random forest accurately predicted 9 transactions with an error out of 506 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.9819 with a specificity of 0.0178 and sensitivity of 0.9968. For the Tensamp dataset, the random forest with 10 decision trees accurately predicted 161 transactions with an error out of 5,193 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.9825 with a specificity of 0.0310 and sensitivity of 0.9975. With 50 decision trees, the random forest accurately predicted 164 transactions with an error out of 5,193 total transactions with an error. This random forest model had an accuracy of 0.9825 with a specificity of 0.0316 and sensitivity of 0.9976. With 100 decision trees, the random forest accurately predicted 168 transactions with an error out of 5,193 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.9825 with a specificity of 0.0324 and sensitivity of 0.9976. For the whole dataset, the random forest with 10 decision trees accurately predicted 4,493 transactions with an error out of 52,821 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.9827 with a specificity of 0.0851 and sensitivity of 0.9972. With 50 decision trees, the random forest accurately predicted 5,011 transactions with an error out of 52,821 total transactions with an error. This random forest model had an accuracy of 0.9829 with a specificity of 0.0949 and sensitivity of 0.9972. With 100 decision trees, the random forest accurately predicted 5,070 transactions with an error out of 52,821 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.9829 with a specificity of 0.09598 and sensitivity of 0.9973. Table 10 shows a comparison between the random forests with 10 trees vs the random forests with 50 trees.

Table 10: Comparison of Results for Random Forests with 10 and 50 Trees

Data	Random Forest with 10 Trees			Random Forest with 50 Trees		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Hunsamp	0.9821	0.0217	0.9969	0.9819	0.0158	0.9968
Tensamp	0.9825	0.0310	0.9975	0.9825	0.0316	0.9976
Whole Dataset	0.9827	0.0851	0.9972	0.9829	0.0949	0.9972

This code was then run into RStudio. I changed any NAs for the zip code into “00000”. The NAs for zip code were just transactions that were online. I also only converted the code for random forests with 100 decision trees. For the Hunsamp dataset, the random forest with 100 decision trees accurately predicted 1 transaction with an error out of 624 total transactions with an error. The accuracy of the model was 0.9844 with a specificity of 0.0016 and a sensitivity of 1. For the Tensamp dataset, the random forest with 100 decision trees accurately predicted 66 transactions with an error out of 6,304 total transactions with an error. The accuracy of the model was 0.9844 with a specificity of 0.0105 and a sensitivity of 1. For the entire dataset, because there was not enough memory, I had to make an additional change to the code. I added a maximum node of 10 and a maximum node size of 10. However, the random forest created did not predict any transactions with an error out of the 63,418 total transactions with an error. It predicted that every transaction did not have an error. Thus, the accuracy was 0.9841 with a specificity of 0 and sensitivity of 1. Table 11 compares the results of the random forest models with 100 trees for each software.

Table 11: Results of Random Forest with 100 Trees

Data	Python			RStudio		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Hunsamp	0.9819	0.0178	0.9968	0.9844	0.0016	1
Tensamp	0.9825	0.0324	0.9976	0.9844	0.0105	1
Whole Dataset	0.9829	0.09598	0.9973	0.9841	0	1

Table 12 compares the running times to create the random forest for each dataset in the two software. RStudio was faster in creating the random forest but had a lower specificity and trouble with memory.

Table 12: Running Time for Random Forest with 100 Trees

Data	RStudio	Python Spyder
Hunsamp	7.02 sec	11.7694 sec
Tensamp	153.77 sec (2.56 min)	234.61 sec (3.9 min)
Whole Dataset	546.30 sec (9.11 min)	3498.46 sec (58.31 min)

The random forest was redone to predict whether the transactions were fraudulent or not. The random forest was created with 100 decision trees. In Python, the random forest model accurately predicted 1,801 fraudulent transactions out of 3,294 total fraudulent transactions. It had an overall accuracy of 0.9989, specificity of 0.5468, and sensitivity of 0.9997. The average time to create the random forest in Python was 25 minutes. When this code was programmed into RStudio, the maximum number of nodes and maximum size of the nodes were changed to 10. I also had to add a small class weight where every fraudulent transaction was weighted as heavy as five non-fraudulent transactions. Without these changes the code would not run due to memory issues. The RStudio random forest accurately predicted 3,118 fraudulent transactions out of 3,311 total fraudulent transactions. Its overall accuracy was 0.8312 with a specificity of 0.9417 and sensitivity of 0.8310. The average time to run this code was 7.7 minutes. Table 13 compares the results of the random forests with 100 trees in Python and RStudio. The code in RStudio performed much better and faster than the code in Python Spyder. This fact might have been because the code had to be modified to take up less memory and class weights were added.

Table 13: Random Forest Results for Combined Dataset

Data	Combined Dataset		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Python	0.9989	0.5468	0.9997
RStudio	0.8312	0.9417	0.8310

The random forests took much longer than the decision trees. In Python Spyder, the decision tree for the entire dataset took on average 1.48 minutes to be created while the random forest took on average 58.31 minutes to be created. This increase in running time was expected since random forests use multiple decision trees. However, the random forests did predict more fraudulent transactions than decision trees.

4.4 Results of Neural Network

I first coded the neural networks in Python Spyder and tested them on all three datasets. Two different neural networks were created for each dataset. One had 50 hidden layers and the other had 100 hidden layers. The class weights were automatically balanced by Python during training. Python adjusted the weights proportional to their class frequencies. This meant that since the frequency of fraudulent transactions was so low, they had more weight than the non-fraudulent transactions. For the Hunsamp dataset, the neural network with 50 hidden layers accurately predicted 321 transactions with an error out of 506 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.6504 with a specificity of 0.6344 and sensitivity of 0.6507. With 100 hidden layers, the neural network accurately predicted 300 transactions with an error out of 506 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.6623 with a specificity of 0.5929 and sensitivity of 0.6634. The neural network with 100 layers had higher accuracy and sensitivity, but a lower specificity. The average run time for 50 hidden layers was 9.77 seconds compared to 14.25 seconds for 100 hidden layers. For the Tensamp dataset, the neural network with 50 hidden layers accurately predicted 2,936 transactions with an error out of 5,193 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.6704 with a specificity of 0.5654 and sensitivity of 0.6721. With 100 hidden layers, the neural network accurately predicted 2,952 transactions with an error out of 5,193 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.6738 with a specificity of 0.5685 and sensitivity of 0.6755. For the whole dataset, the neural network with 50 hidden layers accurately predicted 31,671 transactions with an error out of 52,821 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.6484 with a specificity of 0.5996 and sensitivity of 0.6492. With 100 hidden layers, the neural network accurately predicted 33,110 transactions with an error out of 52,821 total transactions with an error. The accuracy was 0.6211 with a specificity of 0.6268 and sensitivity of 0.6209. The results for the neural networks of 50 and 100 hidden layers are depicted in Table 14.

Table 14: Results of Neural Networks

Data	Neural Network with 50 Hidden Layers			Neural Network with 100 Hidden Layers		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Hunsamp	0.6504	0.6344	0.6507	0.6623	0.5929	0.6634
Tensamp	0.6704	0.5654	0.6721	0.6738	0.5685	0.6755
Whole Dataset	0.6484	0.5996	0.6492	0.6211	0.6268	0.6209

The neural network with 100 layers had higher accuracy and sensitivity, but a lower specificity for the Hunsamp and Tensamp datasets. The average run time for 50 hidden layers was quicker than the time to run for 100 hidden layers. The neural network for the entire dataset with 100 hidden layers was less accurate overall than the neural network with 50 hidden layers but had a higher specificity. This code was then programmed into RStudio, and I only created neural networks with 100 hidden layers. For the Hunsamp dataset, the neural network accurately predicted 190 transactions with an error out of 404 total transactions with an error. The overall accuracy was 0.6887 with a specificity of 0.4703 and sensitivity of 0.6918. For the Tensamp dataset, the neural network accurately predicted 2,657 transactions with an error out of 4,361 total transactions with an error. The overall accuracy was 0.6448 with a specificity of 0.6093 and sensitivity of 0.6453. For

the whole dataset, the neural network accurately predicted 27,651 transactions with an error out of 43,785 total transactions with an error. The overall accuracy was 0.6411 with a specificity of 0.6315 and sensitivity of 0.6413. Table 15 summarizes these results.

Table 15: Results of Neural Network in RStudio

Data	Neural Network with 100 Hidden Layers in RStudio		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Hunsamp	0.6887	0.4703	0.6918
Tensamp	0.6448	0.6093	0.6453
Whole Dataset	0.6411	0.6315	0.6413

The code in RStudio took much longer than the Python Spyder code. For the entire dataset, the neural network with 100 hidden nodes averaged about 13.15 minutes in Python Spyder compared to 4.699 hours for the RStudio code. Table 16 compares the running times to create neural networks for each dataset in the two software.

Table 16: Running Time for Neural Network with 100 Hidden Layers

Data	RStudio	Python Spyder
Hunsamp	399.92 sec (6.67 min)	14.25 sec
Tensamp	4590.71 sec (76.51 min)	121.95 sec (2.03 min)
Whole Dataset	16918.19 sec (4.699 hours)	789.13 sec (13.15 min)

The neural network was redone with the entire banking transactions dataset combined with the JSON file that was also downloaded off Kaggle titled train fraud labels. The neural networks were adjusted to predict which transactions were fraudulent or not. I only created a neural network with 100 hidden layers. In Python Spyder, the neural network accurately predicted 2,665 fraudulent transactions out of 3,294 total fraudulent transactions. The overall accuracy of this model was 0.9685 with a specificity of 0.8090 and sensitivity of 0.9687. The code took about 24.7 minutes to create the neural network. When converted into RStudio, the model accurately predicted 2,956 fraudulent transactions out of 3,311 total fraudulent transactions. It had an accuracy of 0.9243 with a specificity of 0.8928 and sensitivity of 0.9243. The neural network in RStudio took about 6.76 hours to create. Table 17 records the results of these neural networks. Both the specificities and sensitivities of the neural networks were above 0.8. This indicates that the neural networks did a good job of accurately predicting fraudulent transactions. The neural network model performed the best out of all four methods.

Table 17: Neural Network Results for Combined Dataset

Data	Combined Dataset		
	Accuracy	Specificity	Sensitivity
Python	0.9685	0.8090	0.9687
RStudio	0.9243	0.8928	0.9243

5. Conclusion and Future Research

This research focused on four statistical models and machine learning techniques to predict fraudulent transactions. Based on this data and analysis, the neural network machine learning technique worked best. When predicting fraudulent transactions, the logistic regression equation had an accuracy of 0.9985, specificity of 0.0015, and sensitivity of 0.9999. The decision tree had an accuracy of 0.9989, specificity of 0.5458, and sensitivity of 0.9995. The random forest had an accuracy of 0.9989, specificity of 0.5468, and sensitivity of 0.9997. The neural network had an accuracy of 0.9685, specificity of 0.8090, and sensitivity of 0.9687. The final test of each method was to use the JSON file of labeled fraudulent transactions as a training dataset to create each model. Each model was then used to predict which of the remaining 4,390,952 unlabeled transactions were fraudulent. The logistic regression equation predicted there were 29 fraudulent transactions. The decision tree method predicted there were 7,627 fraudulent transactions. The random forest method

predicted there would be 4,935 fraudulent transactions. Lastly, the neural network method predicted there would be 169,322 fraudulent transactions. Based on the accuracy, specificity, and sensitivity of each method under the supervised learning environment, the neural network had the most accurate guess of fraudulent transactions.

These results support the statements made in the literature review section. Alfriyie, et al. (2023), Salunke, et al. (2025), and Randhawa, et al. (2018) concluded that the logistic regression model performed the poorest in predicting fraudulent transactions. Alfriyie, et al. (2023), Salunke, et al. (2025), and Randhawa, et al. (2018), and Prajwala T R (2015) determined the random forest performed better than both decision trees and logistic regression. The neural network method performed the best of the four methods. Mienye and Jere (2024) studied the specificities and sensitivities of machine learning algorithms. They noticed that the sensitivity of each model was very high, while the specificity was lower. Prajwala T R (2015) also concluded that the decision tree was much quicker to run the code in R than the random forest code.

In three out of the four methods, Python Spyder was faster. The only method that RStudio was faster in was random forest. Converting the code to RStudio from Python Spyder was a bit difficult. There were issues with memory when running the code on the entire dataset and any NAs in the dataset would cause an error to occur in RStudio. RStudio also predicted fewer transactions with an error than the Python Spyder code. This difference may be because Python tends to be more sensitive to rare class cases. There could also be some other differences between how the code is run and the randomness in separating the data into a training and testing dataset.

For future research, these models can be further improved to ensure higher accuracy. One way to improve the accuracy of each model is to use a balanced dataset. A balanced dataset would have a similar number of fraudulent and non-fraudulent transactions. To do this, one could separate the fraudulent transactions from the non-fraudulent transactions. Then the non-fraudulent transactions would be under sampled to match the number of fraudulent transactions. The datasets could also be balanced by weighing the fraudulent transactions more than the non-fraudulent transactions. I could also improve the neural network to ensure higher accuracy. The neural network used in this research used automatically balanced weights. With some adjusting, the weights can be even more optimized to give a higher accuracy.

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Appendix

If you need additional details about the Appendix, please contact the author at jlpatrone@student.bridgew.edu.